

PRIME: Next generation electronic medical records for personalised medicine and clinical decision support

D. Gatsios*, G. Rigas** and S. Konitsiotis*

* Department of Neurology, Medical School, University of Ioannina

Ioannina, Greece, d.gatsios@uoi.gr, skonitso@uoi.gr

** Capemed, Ioannina, Greece, g.rigas@capemed.biz

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the 2nd most common neurodegenerative condition affecting more than 6 million people in 2016 [1]. The management of PD is mainly symptomatic, based on the clinical work up and follow up examination as well as to the self-perceived reporting of the symptoms by patients which typically takes place every 3-6 months in most EU healthcare systems. Automated and continuous reporting and evaluation of symptoms and assessment of the response to the prescribed medication is the key for a tailored treatment aiming at its optimization.

Materials and methods

In PRIME the non-motor symptoms will be reported in, an adapted for that purpose, patient portal. The motor symptoms will be passively and automatically evaluated with research and medical grade wearable devices. The backend decision support modules will be exposed in a dashboard designed to support clinicians in the diagnosis and treatment of PD and developed on top of interoperable electronic medical records (EMR).

The research and development activities for the implementation of the clinical decision support system (CDSS) include:

- Machine learning methods that intelligently and automatically analyse all the clinical data of a patient, that are available in the EMR, and create a profile based on similar cases the prescribing clinical has already managed.
- Mechanisms for the detection and elimination of unnecessary, contraindicated or mutually excluded treatments for patients with co-morbidities or multiple drugs as well as taking into account pharmacogenetics information.
- Implementation of an API for the collection of data from Internet of Things (IoT) devices (IMUs, pressure insoles, smartphones, FHIR compliant medical devices).
- Processing of the collected data from the research grade devices and storage in the patient's EMR of information from his daily life so that it becomes possible to periodically assess the course of the disease and the response to treatment and, at the same time, enhance self-management of the disease.
- Design and implementation of the Neurologist-computer interface (dashboard) to guide him in the whole decision-making process following logical

steps and in accordance with clinical practice (Guidelines), in order to prescribe optimal care plans.

Evaluation and Deployment

The suggestions of the CDSS will be evaluated with a series of retrospective use cases by a panel of 3 Movement Disorders Experts. The service will be evaluated in a prospective, proof of concept study in the Neurology Clinic of the University Hospital of Ioannina. Upon its completion, the CDSS will be available as an add-on for the Neurologists using the NetMed360 EMR [2].

Discussion

PRIME aims to add in the evidence of the meaningful and efficient use of EMRs. PRIME will also improve the knowledge about individual course of the disease with ecologically valid data. PRIME will provide a personalized medicine approach for the management of PD by taking into account genetics, clinical subtypes, personality and comorbidity.

The initial application and test case for PRIME is Neurology and specifically Parkinson's which calls for personalized approaches due to its complexity and diversity. Within the framework of PRIME, tools will be developed and evaluated to support Neurologists' decisions for the diagnosis and management as well as to promote self-management approaches from patients.

References

1. E. R. Dorsey *et al.*, "Global, regional, and national burden of Parkinson's disease, 1990–2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016," *Lancet Neurol*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 939-953, 2018.
2. www.netmed360.com/

Keywords:

Parkinson's disease, Electronic Medical Records, Clinical Decision Support System, mhealth

Acknowledgement

PRIME is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH – CREATE – INNOVATE (project code: T2EDK- 05199).